

Offline Cost-Efficient Network and Compute Resource Allocation in 6G Healthcare 4.0

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Abstract—Healthcare 4.0 (H4.0) integrates next-generation wireless technologies, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) to enable globally connected and real-time healthcare services. The stringent coverage requirements suggest an integrated Terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial Network (TN-NTN) domain under a tight coordination of communication and computing resources. In such TN-NTNs, optimising energy efficiency alone is inadequate for sustainable network planning, motivating the need for cost efficient strategies to mitigate infrastructure deployment expenses while preserving service quality. To address this challenge, we propose an offline cost-aware-based joint network and compute resource allocation framework that optimizes user association, traffic routing, and any-type Network Function (xNF) placement over healthcare-oriented Service Function Chains (SFCs) aligned with the latest ITU-R requirements for IMT-2030. The problem is formulated as a Mixed Integer Linear Program (MILP) minimizing the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO), while addressing the associated computational complexity, a heuristic approach, termed CHEUR, is proposed and evaluated through simulations. Simulation results indicate that CHEUR achieves near-optimal performance while reducing computational complexity by approximately 96% compared to the optimal solution. Moreover, it delivers up to 75% TCO reduction compared to the state-of-the-art approaches and attains up to 89% of the optimal TCO performance throughout the day, thereby validating its suitability for scalable, sustainable, and cost-aware deployment of 6G-H4.0 networks.

Index Terms—6G, cost-efficiency, green networks, healthcare, service function chains (SFCs), TN-NTNs.

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), big data, AI/ML and cloud/Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) have paved the way for Healthcare 4.0 (H4.0), shifting care from hospital-centric to patient-centric through real-time, data-driven intelligence. With 6G’s ultra-reliable, low-latency communication, H4.0 can support real-time telemedicine, remote surgery, and continuous monitoring via smart connected devices. Unlike 5G, which offers limited support for immersive applications, 6G-enabled H4.0 (6G-H4.0) will leverage the Internet of Skills (IoS) and the tactile Internet to enable bi-directional, skill-based human-machine interaction, revolutionizing telehealth and precision medicine [1].

As data-intensive and latency-critical applications continue to proliferate, current networks struggle to meet Internet of Everything (IoE) demands. This challenge has accelerated the evolution towards 6G, envisioned as a unified Terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial Network (TN-NTN) architecture integrating

ground, aerial, and satellite systems to deliver ultra-high data rates, massive connectivity, ultra-low latency, high reliability, and global coverage. Despite these advantages, NTN introduces significant capital (CAPEX) and operational (OPEX) expenditures due to the high deployment, maintenance, and energy costs of satellite constellations and aerial platforms, making cost-aware network planning a critical requirement for sustainable 6G-H4.0 deployments.

However, beyond the network infrastructure and its operation, the computational dimension plays an equally critical role in enabling H4.0 services, as advanced medical applications increasingly leverage distributed processing across edge, fog, and cloud resources. Network Function Virtualization (NFV) with MEC or cloud computing [2] is a key enabler, replacing dedicated hardware with flexible, scalable any-type Network Function (xNFs) deployed on shared infrastructure. Dynamic xNF placement, migration, and termination can significantly reduce CAPEX/OPEX and improve service agility, although optimal deployment remains challenging due to load balancing, service chaining, latency, and resource variability. Such challenges motivate the need for offline planning frameworks that allow operators to evaluate deployment, cost, and performance trade-offs in advance, before real-time operation.

Therefore, the aforementioned challenges call for joint, cost-aware network planning frameworks that coordinate network and computational resources across 6G infrastructures, to satisfy the stringent Quality of Service (QoS) requirements of H4.0 applications, and deliver both optimal Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) benchmarks and scalable, low-complexity solutions for practical deployment.

A. State-of-the-Art and Contribution

Prior work in TNs have addressed joint optimization of xNF placement and computational Resource Allocation (RA) in the core/cloud segment [3], [4], as well as coordinated User Association (UA) with spectrum RA [5]. Recent studies extend these ideas to TN-NTN scenarios [6]–[10], considering joint UA, routing, and xNF placement with an emphasis on Energy Efficiency (EE) and OPEX reduction [6], [8]. However, these approaches neglect CAPEX-related deployment and equipment costs, which are key drivers of infrastructure planning and TCO in 6G TN-NTN networks.

While cost-aware xNF placement has been explored in cloud and MEC environments [11], [12], such studies typically

Fig. 1: Illustration of a typical 6G TN-NTN domain topology with deployed xNFs.

assume homogeneous terrestrial infrastructures and do not account for the heterogeneous, high cost, and heavily-constrained NTN components, including satellites and aerial platforms. Consequently, existing optimization frameworks fail to model the infrastructure-driven trade-offs in integrated TN-NTN architectures, where performance and EE objectives are inherently constrained by deployment density and associated CAPEX. Hence, current approaches fall short of meeting the stringent latency, reliability, throughput, and global coverage requirements of H4.0 applications.

To address these challenges, in this paper, we propose a cost-aware optimization framework for mission-critical medical services in an integrated 6G TN-NTN architecture spanning terrestrial (gNodeBs (gNBs), Small Cells (SCs)) and non-terrestrial (aerial, satellite) Base Stations (BSs), supporting both wireless access and hybrid wireless/fiber X-haul transport. The proposed framework jointly optimizes UA, traffic routing, and xNF placement across the compute continuum (edge, fog, cloud) while explicitly modeling both cost and power consumption. It comprises an optimal problem formulation that establishes TCO benchmarks, together with a scalable, low-complexity heuristic solution (CHEUR), achieving lower TCO compared to commonly adopted State-Of-the-Art (SoA) approaches [13]. Designed as an offline network planning tool, the proposed framework enables operators to quantitatively assess how different deployment and resource allocation choices impact TCO, energy consumption, and computational placement in sustainable 6G-H4.0 deployments.

The rest of the paper consists of: Section II introduces the system model and the studied problem; Section III describes the proposed heuristic; Section IV discusses the evaluation framework; Section V concludes the paper with future work.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND STUDIED PROBLEM

We extend the framework of [6] by incorporating cost metrics accounting for both CAPEX, which is associated with infrastructure deployment, and OPEX, which is linked to resource utilization. The network is modeled as a heterogeneous multi-tier mobile architecture comprising Radio Access

Network (RAN) and core segments, represented by a directed graph $\mathcal{G}(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$, where \mathcal{V} is the set of nodes and \mathcal{E} the set of directed links, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The node set \mathcal{V} comprises terrestrial (gNBs, SCs), aerial (Low Altitude Platforms (LAPS), High Altitude Platforms (HAPS)), and space nodes (Low Earth Orbit (LEO)), collectively referred to as BSs, in the RAN, along with switches and computational nodes in the core. The latter elements are generally implemented as xNFs deployed on virtual instances such as Virtual Machines (VMs) or containers, which leverage computational resources collocated with the corresponding link network nodes. Every node $y \in \mathcal{V}$ incurs an operational cost $C_{\text{OPEX},y}$ and a one-time equipment acquisition cost $C_{\text{CAPEX},y}$. Each link $e = (u, v) \in \mathcal{E}$ connects nodes $u, v \in \mathcal{V}$ and represents either a wired (e.g., fiber) or wireless (e.g., millimeter wave (mmWave), Free-Space Optical (FSO), Inter-Satellite Link (ISL)) medium. The set \mathcal{E} is partitioned into wired \mathcal{E}^{fi} and wireless \mathcal{E}^{wl} links. Links are characterized by capacity c_e (Mbps), latency δ_e (ms), and cost $C_e = C_{\text{CAPEX},e} + C_{\text{OPEX},e}$, where $C_{\text{CAPEX},e}$ reflects the deployment cost and $C_{\text{OPEX},e}$ is the utilization-dependent operational cost.

The set of User Equipments (UEs) is denoted by \mathcal{J} , and the extended node set as $\mathcal{V} \triangleq \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{J}$. Each UE $j \in \mathcal{J}$ associates with a candidate access set $A(j) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, which includes access nodes satisfying minimum signal quality constraints. Here, $A \triangleq \bigcup_{j \in \mathcal{J}} A(j)$ is defined as a set of all BSs. A base station $a \in A$ provides $N_a^{(\text{RB})}$ Resource Blocks (RBs), distributed among UEs in its coverage region $S(a) = \{j \in \mathcal{J} \mid a \in A(j)\}$. Nodes capable of hosting xNFs constitute the subset $\mathcal{V}_c \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, where each computational node $y \in \mathcal{V}_c$ offers c_y GFLOPS and incurs corresponding CAPEX and OPEX. xNFs are drawn from the set \mathcal{F} , where each $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is represented by the tuple $(T_f, \pi_f, w_f, \tau_f)$ denoting its type T_f , CPU demand (GFLOPS) π_f , per-Mbps processing load w_f , and processing delay τ_f (ms). Let \mathcal{H} be the set of SFCs, where each Service Function Chain (SFC) $\rho \in \mathcal{H}$ is defined as an ordered sequence $\rho = \langle f_1^{(\rho)}, \dots, f_{N_\rho}^{(\rho)} \rangle$, enforcing sequential traversal of xNFs. We denote $f \rightsquigarrow \rho$ to indicate that xNF f belongs to ρ , and define $\mathcal{R}_\rho = \{f \in \mathcal{F} \mid f \rightsquigarrow \rho\}$. Each UE $j \in \mathcal{J}$ requests a service $q_j = (s_{q_j}, r_{q_j}, \delta_{q_j}, \rho_{q_j}) \in \mathcal{Q}$, where $s_{q_j} \in \mathcal{V}$ is the traffic source, r_{q_j} is the data rate (Mbps), δ_{q_j} is the end-to-end delay budget (ms), and $\rho_{q_j} \in \mathcal{H}$ is the requested SFC. Multiple xNFs can be hosted on a single node and shared among UEs, provided that the aggregate demand does not exceed the node's hosting capacity. For each UE j , the number of RBs $N_{a,j}^{(\text{RB})}$ on access link $(a, j) \in \mathcal{E}$ is determined from the estimated signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) $\sigma_{a,j}$ and rate r_{q_j} [6].

The optimization problem involves the following boolean decision variables: $x_{j,a} \triangleq \mathbb{I}[\text{UE } j \text{ is connected to BS } a]$, $\phi_{\bar{y},f,q} \triangleq \mathbb{I}[\text{xNF } f \text{ of service } q \text{ is hosted on node } \bar{y}]$, and $\theta_{e',q} = \theta_{u,v}^{e',q} \triangleq \mathbb{I}[e = (u, v) \in \mathcal{E} \text{ is used in the physical path onto which the virtual link } e' \in \mathcal{E}(\rho_q) \text{ is mapped for SFC } \rho_q]$ [6]. For each fiber link $e = (n, m) \in \mathcal{E}^{fi}$. Let ξ_y be a Boolean variable that indicates whether node y executes any deployed xNFs. Furthermore, $N_{f,\bar{y}}$ represents the number of xNF f

instances instantiated on node \tilde{y} . To improve cost efficiency, computing resources, links, and nodes are deployed only when required.

A. Problem Formulation

The offline cost-efficient optimization problem is formulated as the following Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP):

$$\text{argmin TCO,} \quad \text{s.t. (3)–(10),} \quad (1)$$

where all decision variables are boolean or integer as defined above. Here, TCO is expressed as $\text{TCO} = \sum_{z \in X_{\text{deployed}}} (\text{C}_{\text{CAPEX},z} + \text{C}_{\text{OPEX},z})$, where X_{deployed} is the set of all deployed infrastructure elements (terrestrial, aerial or space), i.e., $X_{\text{deployed}} = A_{\text{deployed}} \cup \mathcal{V}_{c,\text{deployed}} \cup \mathcal{E}_{\text{deployed}}$ where, A_{deployed} is the set of deployed nodes (e.g., gNBs, SCs, LAPS, HAPS), $\mathcal{V}_{c,\text{deployed}}$ is the set of deployed computational nodes, $\mathcal{E}_{\text{deployed}}$ is the set of deployed communication links (e.g., fiber, mmWave). The CAPEX of an infrastructure element z is incurred only if that element is deployed and is defined as $\text{C}_{\text{CAPEX},z} = c_z \cdot \phi_z$, where c_z is the fixed deployment cost of element z and $\phi_z \in \{0, 1\}$ is a binary decision variable indicating whether element z is deployed or not. The annual OPEX for each deployed element z is

$$\text{C}_{\text{OPEX},z} = (P_z \cdot g \cdot H) + C_{\text{maint},z}. \quad (2)$$

where $\text{C}_{\text{OPEX},z}$ is the annual OPEX for element z , P_z is the power consumption of element z in kilowatts (kW) and power models for each node or link type are taken from [6], [8], g is the average electricity price in euros per kilowatt-hour (€/kWh), $C_{\text{maint},z}$ is the yearly maintenance cost for compute node z , and H is the number of hours in a year (used to annualize energy costs).

Let ψ_n be the Boolean variable indicating whether the switch at node $n \in \mathcal{V}_{sw}$ forwards actual traffic. The relation-ship among these deployment variables is enforced through

$$\sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \sum_{e' \in \mathcal{E}(\rho_q)} \theta_{e'}^{e',q} \leq C_1 w_e, \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E}^{fi}. \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}^{fi}: h(e)=n} w_e + \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}^{fi}: t(e)=n} w_e \leq C_1 \psi_n, \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{V}_{sw}. \quad (4)$$

where $C_1 > 0$ is a sufficiently large constant and $h(e), t(e)$ are the head and tail nodes of link e , respectively. These conditions ensure that a switch node is deployed ($\psi_n = 1$) only when it has at least one deployed link, and that a link is deployed solely if it transports service traffic.

Following the approach in [6], we linearize deployment and power-saving relations by introducing auxiliary Boolean variables σ_e for $e \in \mathcal{E}^{wl}$ and ν_a for $a \in \mathcal{A}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_e + C_2 \sigma_e &\geq 1, \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E}^{wl}, \\ 1 - C_2 \chi_e &\leq \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \sum_{e' \in \mathcal{E}(\rho_q)} \theta_{e'}^{e',q} \leq C_2 (1 - \sigma_e), \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E}^{wl}, \\ 1 - C_1 \nu_a &\leq \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} x_{j,a} \leq C_2 (1 - \nu_a), \mu_a + C_1 \nu_a \geq 1, \forall a \in \mathcal{A}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Each service request must have all its required xNFs placed on one node, and each UE must connect to exactly one allowable BS:

$$\sum_{y \in \mathcal{V}_c} \phi_{y,f,q} = 1, \forall q \in \mathcal{Q}, \forall f \in \mathcal{R}_q, \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}(j)} x_{j,a} = 1, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}. \quad (6)$$

Constraints which ensure that i) the deployed xNF instances on a node meet the data processing requirements without exceeding the available CPU resources, and ii) computational nodes are deployed only when required are formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}: f \rightsquigarrow \rho_q} \phi_{y,f,q} r_q &\leq N_{f,y} \pi_f, \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F}, \forall y \in \mathcal{V}_c, \\ \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} N_{f,y} w_f &\leq c_y, \forall y \in \mathcal{V}_c, \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} N_{f,y} \leq C_1 \xi_y, \forall y \in \mathcal{V}_c. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The capacity constraints for links and BSs are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{q \in \mathcal{Q}} \sum_{e' \in \mathcal{E}(\rho_q)} \theta_{e'}^{e',q} r_q &\leq c_e, \quad \forall e \in \mathcal{E}, \\ \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}(a)} N_{a,j}^{(\text{RB})} &\leq N_a^{(\text{RB})}, \quad \forall a \in \mathcal{A}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The flow conservation and routing requirements are

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{v:(u,v) \in \mathcal{E}} \theta_{u,v}^{e',q} - \sum_{w:(w,u) \in \mathcal{E}} \theta_{w,u}^{e',q} &= \phi_{u,h(e'),q} - \phi_{u,t(e'),q}, \\ \forall q \in \mathcal{Q}, \forall e' \in \mathcal{E}(\rho_q), \forall u \in \tilde{\mathcal{V}}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The E2E delay constraints for each user service q_j is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{V}_c} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{R}_{q_j}} \phi_{y,f,q_j} \tau_f + \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \sum_{e' \in \mathcal{E}(\rho_{q_j})} \theta_{e'}^{e',q_j} \delta_e \\ + \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}(j)} x_{j,a} \delta_{(a,j)} \leq \delta_{q_j}, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Due to the high complexity (NP-hardness) of the optimal solution, we propose a low-complexity cost-efficient network planning algorithm in Section III.

III. COST-AWARE NETWORK PLANNING HEURISTIC ALGORITHM (CHEUR)

An offline, cost-efficient heuristic termed CHEUR is introduced to jointly optimize UA, traffic routing, and xNF placement with the goal of minimizing overall TCO, while ensuring that all UEs requests are satisfied. As illustrated in Fig. 2, CHEUR operates in two sequential stages: (i) UA and routing, (ii) xNF placement in the sequence specified by the SFC. Defining the user examination order is done so as to ensure that the maximum number of UEs are accepted with the lowest number of deployed nodes. To maximize the UE acceptance ratio, UEs are prioritized according to their service requirements, with precedence given to those with the most stringent latency constraints. Among UEs sharing the same delay requirements, higher priority is assigned to those with greater data rate demands. For each UE, a weighted graph is constructed that represents all feasible paths from the source node to the destination UE. The link weights reflect

Fig. 2: Flowchart of Proposed Offline Heuristic for Cost-Efficient UA, Traffic Routing and xNF Placement (CHEUR).

the total network cost, integrating both CAPEX and OPEX for X-haul and access links. Furthermore, CHEUR exploits resource reuse by allowing shared utilization of xNFs and links already deployed for previously processed UEs, thereby improving cost effectiveness. The algorithm then determines the k shortest least-cost paths and selects the one with the minimum overall cost that satisfies the required delay and capacity constraints, considering the decisions already made for previous UEs. After each UE is admitted, the residual capacity and utilization-dependent cost of the links along the selected path are updated to reflect the additional carried traffic. When the selected path fails to meet any of these constraints, the next path in the ordered list is evaluated. If no feasible path exists, the UE is marked as blocked, and the algorithm proceeds with the remaining users. After identifying a valid path, CHEUR advances to the second stage, the xNF placement. For each xNF in the SFC sequence, a set of candidate computational nodes is generated. Each node is characterized by its closeness centrality (since nodes with higher centrality typically lie on a larger number of shortest paths and therefore provide better connectivity and traffic aggregation capabilities. Prioritizing such nodes for xNF placement improves overall resource utilization and reduces infrastructure deployment cost), CAPEX, and associated OPEX, which depends on the load and type of the node. CHEUR evaluates the TCO for each candidate node along the chosen path. The TCO consists of the sum of additional CAPEX (depending on the cost per GFLOPS used and the node’s specifications) and any additional OPEX if a new instance is instantiated. Three deployment scenarios are considered: a) If the xNF can be accommodated on an already deployed node without exceeding its processing

capacity or requiring a new instance, the additional cost is zero. b) If the node is deployed but requires a new xNF instance, only the corresponding OPEX is incurred. c) If the node is not deployed and a new instance must be deployed, both additional CAPEX and OPEX are accounted for. The node with the minimum TCO (weighted sum) and the most favourable centrality, while meeting computational capacity constraints, is selected to host the xNF. If no suitable node is found along the selected path, CHEUR backtracks and evaluates the next available path among the k shortest-cost options. This iterative process continues until all xNFs within the UE’s SFC are successfully placed or all candidate paths have been evaluated. Upon successful placement of all xNFs, the network state is updated, and CHEUR proceeds to the next UE. This process of selecting node deployment repeats until all UEs have been processed.

IV. EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

A. Simulation Scenario

We evaluate the performance of the optimal solution, developed in IBM CPLEX, with our proposed heuristic algorithm (CHEUR) and SoA [13] in MATLAB R2024b in an Apple M3 processor and 16 GB RAM. Based on a predefined traffic model across gNB sectors (Fig.3) [14], and for a given number of UEs, we run ten different BS distribution scenarios, with ten UE hotspot traffic distribution snapshots each.

The simulated topology considers a 500 m radius macrocell centered on a gNB in Thessaloniki, Greece [8], with 2 SC clusters, each comprising 4 SCs uniformly and randomly distributed within a 100 m radius. The gNB and one randomly selected SC per cluster is assumed to have fiber access to a two-tier transport network (fog and cloud), each containing nodes that have connection amongst them and with the BSs via fiber to ensure full connectivity. Additionally, mmWave X-haul links are also assumed between any pair of BSs within 200 m. Key parameters for the access (gNB, SC, LAPS, HAPS, LEO) and backhaul (Wireless Transport Network (WTN), TN-NTN, Air-to-Space (A2S), Air-to-Air (A2A), ISL) networks are summarized in Table I and the rest of the parameter values are taken from [6]. The NTN segment comprises 1 Iridium, 15 OneWeb, 25 Starlink, 5 LAPS and 5 HAPS, providing continuous Line of Sight (LoS) connectivity, with orbital data obtained from publicly available ephemerides [15]. Each BS is allocated 100 orthogonal RBs and frequency reuse across SC clusters may induce inter-cluster interference. Satellite and ISL links operate in high-frequency bands, where interference is negligible due to highly directional beamforming. We evaluate 7 SFC types (in Table II). Each SFC is defined by its data rate range, latency requirement, and traffic share, along with processing and CPU demands [6].

B. Simulation Results

This section presents the simulation results comparing the optimal solution, our proposed heuristic (CHEUR), and the SoA benchmark [13]. All three algorithms achieve 100% user acceptance ratio across all time instants. The average TCO

Fig. 3: Traffic pattern throughout the day with high and low traffic periods.

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters [6], [8].

Access Network	gNB	SC	LAPS	HAPS	LEO
f [GHz]	2	2	28	28	28
BW [GHz]	0.02	0.02	0.2	0.2	0.4
C_{CAPEX} [k€]	168	30	200	500	155
C_{maint} [k€/yr]	0.34	0.1	0.8	1	5
Backhaul Network	WTN	A2A	A2S	TN-NTN	ISL
f [GHz]	28	28	28	28	200000
BW [GHz]	0.2	0.6	0.6	0.6	20
C_{CAPEX} [k€]	33	155	200	37	300
C_{maint} [k€/yr]	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3

TABLE II: Details of each SFC [6], [8], [16].

Type of SFC	Data Rate (Mbps)	Delay (ms)	Traffic Share (%)
Telesurgery	[1–5]	170	10
Health Monitoring	[2–5]	50	10
Web Service	[0.6–1]	500	20
VoIP	[0.384–0.64]	100	10
Video Streaming	[5–24]	100	30
Wearable Biometric Telemetry	[0.24–0.5]	60	10
Ultra RT AI/ML	[15–25]	1	10

results in Fig. 4 show that the SoA approach consistently yields the highest TCO across all time slots, as it prioritizes feasibility over cost efficiency, resulting in the deployment of a larger number of terrestrial and aerial nodes (Fig. 5). This effect is particularly evident during peak demand hours (6th–20th), where the continued reliance on energy intensive gNBs, rather than efficient leveraging of SCs and LAPS, leads to a smooth but steep increase in energy and maintenance expenses. In contrast, CHEUR achieves significantly lower TCO throughout the entire day by deploying a minimal set of low-cost nodes, and selectively deploys additional resources during high-demand periods, maintaining a balanced trade-off between CAPEX usage and OPEX growth. The optimal solution consistently provides the lowest TCO over time, since the MILP formulation minimizes the global TCO cost. The resulting curve follows the same overall trend as the proposed algorithm but with some noticeable local fluctuations compared with the heuristic methods, particularly when small demand changes trigger node-deployment decisions.

Fig. 5 illustrates the average number of deployed BSs under peak-load (235 UEs) and low-load (13 UEs) conditions. In network planning, the peak-hour traffic demand determines the

Fig. 4: Comparison of average TCO between optimal, CHEUR and SoA over time in logarithmic scale throughout the day.

Fig. 5: Comparison of average number of deployed BSs between optimal, CHEUR and SoA throughout the day.

maximum number and types of BSs that must be deployed to guarantee service continuity. Under peak load, the optimal solution deploys 5 SCs, CHEUR deploys 7 SCs and 1 LEO satellite, whereas the SoA deploys 1 gNB, 4 SCs, and 4 LAPS, leading to a significantly higher infrastructure footprint and TCO. During low-loads, the deployed infrastructure is not fully utilized, where BSs that are not required to meet current demands are not deployed. Under such conditions, the optimal solution deploys only 1 SC, CHEUR deploys 2 SCs, while SoA requires 1 gNB, 1 SC, and 2 LAPS, reflecting its reliance on costlier BS types. By favouring cost-efficient and spatially dense SC deployments and satellite nodes (LEOs) over gNBs and aerial platforms especially in peak-hours, CHEUR enables effective BS deployment, resulting in substantial TCO savings up to 75% compared to SoA (Fig. 4) and achieves up to 89% of the optimal TCO throughout the day. A similar trend is observed in Fig. 6, where CHEUR deploys fiber links instead of wireless backhaul (BH) links. This choice enables further savings through link deployment.

In addition, CHEUR achieves approximately 96% lower complexity compared to the optimal solution (Fig. 7), as the latter relies on solving a large-scale MILP whose computational complexity grows exponentially with network size and traffic load. By decomposing the problem into tractable sub-tasks for UA, routing, and xNF placement, CHEUR enables efficient offline network planning while maintaining reasonable proximity to the optimal cost. Although offline network plan-

Fig. 6: Comparison of average number of deployed links and computational links between optimal, CHEUR and SoA throughout the day.

ning does not impose stringent execution-time requirements, achieving low runtime enhances practical implementation, repeated scenario evaluation, and operational use by network engineers. In this regard, CHEUR offers a favourable balance between computational efficiency and performance.

Fig. 7: Comparison of average execution time between optimal, CHEUR and SoA over time in logarithmic scale throughout the day.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper investigates offline cost-aware network planning for H4.0 services in integrated 6G TN-NTNs, where both communication and computing resources must be jointly optimized under stringent QoS constraints. An optimal MILP model is formulated that jointly considers UA, traffic routing, and xNF placement with the objective of minimizing the TCO. To overcome the computational complexity of the optimal solution, we develop CHEUR, a scalable and cost-efficient heuristic that explicitly accounts for additional CAPEX and OPEX in its decision-making process. Through extensive simulations, we demonstrate that CHEUR achieves near-optimal performance while significantly reducing computational complexity. In particular, CHEUR lowers TCO up to 75% compared to the SoA and achieves up to 89% of the optimal TCO, and also approximately achieving 96% reduction in complexity relative to the optimal. These results confirm that CHEUR enables cost-effective and sustainable 6G network planning, while maintaining the stringent reliability, latency, and throughput

requirements of H4.0 applications. Future work will extend this framework toward online and adaptive resource allocation and orchestration, enabling real-time decision-making under dynamic traffic demands in 6G-H4.0 environments.

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